

Supplementary Material Table S1

Table S1. Location of Motus towers within the study area forest fragments ($n = 29$) on the north shore of Lake Erie, near Port Rowan (42.7131°N, 80.5372°W) in Norfolk County, Ontario Canada.

Motus Tower	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)
Walsingham	42.6353	80.5577
Langton	42.7259	80.5625
Turkey Point	42.7102	80.3573
Zorad	42.7877	80.4036
Anderson	42.6728	80.5033
Arthur Langford	42.6945	80.6478
BSC	42.6154	80.4581
Old Cut	42.5829	80.3984
Clear Creek	42.5819	80.5763
Bolin	42.6226	80.7218
Falconer Farm	42.8142	80.5849
Werden	42.7546	80.2708
Waterford Quarry	42.9155	80.3108

Supplementary Material Table S2

Table S2. Full set of temporal models for nest daily survival estimates for Wood Thrush in southern Ontario. Models are ranked by Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) with small sample size adjustment (AICc), with number of parameters (k), and model weight (w_i) given for each model.

Model	k	ΔAIC	w_i
\sim Nest age	2	0.00 ^a	1.00
\sim Constant	1	22.36	0.00
\sim Time	2	24.33	0.00
\sim Year	3	25.31	0.00
\sim Time ²	3	26.27	0.00

^a AICc = 1080.3

Supplementary Material Table S3

Table S3: Full set of models for nest daily survival estimates for Wood Thrush in southern Ontario using *nest age* (age) as the base model and three spatial scales for % forest cover (FC) (500 m, 2 km, 5 km), nest parasitism (BHCO), distance to forest edge (DistFE) and forest fragment size (FS). Models are ranked by Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) with small sample size adjustment (AICc), with number of parameters (k), and model weight (w_i) given for each model.

Model	k	ΔAIC	w_i
S ~ age + % FC 5 km	3	0.00 ^a	0.13
S ~ age + BHCO + % FC 5 km	4	0.25	0.11
S ~ age + BHCO	3	0.90	0.08
S ~ age	2	1.31	0.07
S ~ age + DistFE + % FC 5 km	4	1.94	0.05
S ~ age + FS + % FC 5 km	4	2.00	0.05
S ~ age + BHCO * % FC 5 km	5	2.06	0.05
S ~ age + FS + % FC 5 km + BHCO	5	2.21	0.04
S ~ age + FS + BHCO	4	2.58	0.04
S ~ age + BHCO + % FC 2 km	4	2.66	0.03
S ~ age + FS * % FC 5 km	5	2.67	0.03
S ~ age + BHCO + % FC 500 m	4	2.89	0.03
S ~ age + % FC 2 km	3	3.08	0.03
S ~ age + FS	3	3.10	0.03
S ~ age + BHCO * % FC 2 km	5	3.13	0.03
S ~ age + DistFE	3	3.30	0.02
S ~ age + % FC 500 m	3	3.31	0.02
S ~ age + DistFE * % FC 5 km	5	3.42	0.02
S ~ age + FS + % FC 5 km + DistFE	5	3.86	0.02
S ~ age + BHCO * % FC 500 m	5	4.29	0.02
S ~ age + FS * BHCO	5	4.29	0.02
S ~ age + FS + % FC 500 m + BHCO	5	4.33	0.02
S ~ age + FS + % FC 2 km + BHCO	5	4.60	0.01
S ~ age + FS + % FC 500 m	4	4.87	0.01
S ~ age + DistFE + % FC 2 km	4	5.02	0.01
S ~ age + FS + DistFE	4	5.06	0.01

S ~ age + DistFe + % FC 500 m	4	5.30	0.01
S ~ age + DistFE * % FC 500 m	5	6.35	0.01
S ~ age + DistFE * % FC 2 km	5	6.55	0.01
S ~ age + FS * % FC 500 m	5	6.86	0.00
S ~ age + FS + % FC 500 m + DistFE	5	6.88	0.00
S ~ age + FS + % FC 2 km + DistFE	5	6.99	0.00
S ~ age + FS * DistFE	5	7.03	0.00
S ~ age + FS * % FC 2 km	5	7.06	0.00
S ~ constant	1	28.50	0.00

^a AICc = 1097.30

Supplementary Material Table S4

Table S4. Full set of time-dependent models for determining the probability of detecting live tagged (p) fledgling Wood Thrush across 29 forest fragments in southern Ontario over a 3-year survey period, 2016-2018 ($n=189$ fledglings). Models were run holding S (survival) constant, r (~ 1) and F ($=1$).

Parameters included calendar year (Year), linearly changing with age (Age), fledge date (FD) and 2 age categories of 2 (age2) and 3 (age3) age groups. Models are ranked by Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) with small sample size adjustment (AICc), with number of parameters (k), and model weight (w_i) given for each model.

Model	k	ΔAIC	w_i
~ age3 + year	7	0.00 ^a	0.59
~ age3	5	1.35	0.30
~ age3 + FD	6	3.38	0.11
~ Age + year	6	26.21	0.00
~ Age	4	27.66	0.00
~ Age + FD	5	29.66	0.00
~age2 + year	6	32.04	0.00
~ age2	4	33.48	0.00
~ age2 + FD	5	35.48	0.00
~ year	5	37.92	0.00
~ 1	3	39.71	0.00

~ year+ FD	6	39.96	0.00
~ FD	4	41.66	0.00

^a AICc = 929.07

Supplementary Material Table S5

Table S5. Full model set of time-dependent models for Wood Thrush fledgling survival (S) across 29 forest fragments in southern Ontario over a 3-year survey period, 2016-2018 ($n = 189$ fledglings). For all models p (probability of detecting a live tagged fledgling) was modelled as $p(\text{age3} + \text{Year})$.

Survival models included calendar year (Year), linearly changes with age (Age), non-linearly changes with age (Age²), time dependent (Time), fledge date (FD), and 3 age categories of 2 (age2), 3 (age3) and 4 (age4) age groupings. Models are ranked by Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) with small sample size adjustment (AICc), with number of parameters (k), and model weight (w_i) given for each model.

Model	k	ΔAIC	w_i
~ Age	8	0.00 ^a	0.26
~ Age + FD	9	2.00	0.10
~ age3	9	2.03	0.10
~ Age ²	9	2.05	0.09
~ age2	8	2.49	0.08
~ age4	10	2.90	0.06
~ Age + year	10	4.96	0.06
~ age3 + FD	10	4.06	0.03
~ Age ² + FD	10	4.06	0.03
~ age2 + FD	9	4.52	0.03
~ Time	11	4.64	0.03
~ age4 + FD	11	4.92	0.02
~age3 + year	11	4.97	0.02
~ Age ² + year	11	5.02	0.02
~Age + year + FD	11	5.02	0.02
~age2 + year	10	5.47	0.01
~age4 + year	12	5.86	0.00

~age3 + year + FD	12	7.04	0.00
~ age2 + FD + year	11	7.53	0.00
~ age4 + FD + year	13	7.94	0.00
~1	7	15.81	0.00
~ FD	8	17.74	0.00
~ year	9	18.69	0.00
~ year + FD	10	20.71	0.00
~Age ² + year + FD	12	51.07	0.00
~Time + year	13	51.85	0.00

^a AICc = 913.25

Supplementary Material Table S6

Table S6. Full environmental model set for Wood Thrush fledgling survival across 29 forest fragments in southern Ontario over a 3-year survey period, 2016-2018 (n=189 fledglings). Survival models used the base temporal model ($S(Age) p(age3 + Year)$) and additional covariates of forest fragment size (FS), % forest cover (FC) at three spatial scales (500 m, 2 km, 5 km), nestling body condition (BC), mean # of trees with DBH >30cm (DBH), and mean % shrub and sapling cover (SC). Models are ranked by Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) with small sample size adjustment (AICc), with number of parameters (k), and model weight (w_i) given for each model.

Model	k	ΔAIC	w_i
~ Age + BC	8	0.00 ^a	0.20
~Age + % FC 2 km + BC	9	1.38	0.10
~Age	7	1.58	0.09
~Age + % FC 500 m + BC	9	1.95	0.07
~Age + % FC 5 km + BC	9	2.07	0.07
~ Age+ % FC 2 km	8	2.90	0.05
~Age + % SC	8	3.17	0.04
~Age + FS	8	3.37	0.04
~ Age + % FC 2 km * BC	10	3.43	0.04

~Age + % FC 500 m	8	3.53	0.03
~Age + DBH	8	3.62	0.03
~ Age+ % FC 5 km	8	3.63	0.03
~Age + %FC 500 m * BC	10	4.01	0.03
~ Age+ % FC 5 km * BC	10	4.03	0.03
~ Age + % FC 2 km + % SC	9	4.66	0.02
~Age + FS + % FC 2 km	9	4.91	0.02
~ Age + % FC 2 km + DBH	9	4.95	0.02
~Age + FS + % SC	9	5.09	0.02
~Age+ FS + % FC 500 m	9	5.42	0.01
~Age + FS + DBH	9	5.43	0.01
~Age + % FC 2 km * % SC	10	5.55	0.01
~Age + % FC 500 m + DBH	9	5.59	0.01
~Age + % FC 5 km * DBH	10	5.65	0.01
~Age+ FS * % FC 5 km	10	6.35	0.01
~Age+ FS * % FC 2 km	10	6.68	0.01
~Age + FS * DBH	10	6.77	0.01
~Age + FS * % SC	10	7.15	0.01
~Age + FS + BC	9	47.26	0.00
~Age + FS * BC	10	49.31	0.00
~Age + % FC 5 km +% SC	9	49.73	0.00
~Age + % FC 500 m +% SC	9	49.99	0.00
~Age+ FS + % FC 5 km	9	50.92	0.00
~Age + % FC 500 m * % SC	10	50.98	0.00
~Age + % FC 5 km + DBH	9	51.04	0.00
~Age + % FC 2 km * % SC	10	51.93	0.00
~Age + % FC 500 m * DBH	10	51.94	0.00
~Age+ FS * % FC 500 m	10	52.68	0.00
~Age + % FC 2 km * DBH	10	52.97	0.00

^a AICc = 899.29

Supplementary Material S7 – Departure Date

Motus tower data records were accessed using the *motus* and *motusData* R packages and cleaned following guidelines provided by Birds Canada (2022). The Motus filter was applied to flag detections that had a run length < 3 to minimize false positive records but on occasion were incorporated when there were additional supporting detections such as filling a time gap between towers with positive detections (< 5 instances). Subsequently, we manually reviewed all detections (individual hits received by each tower) that the Motus filter had flagged as true positives and removed any that had different pulse rates to 12.7 sec, occurred in unlikely locations (e.g., outside the breeding range), or were well outside of migration routes that have been identified for Wood Thrush in previous geolocator studies (Stutchbury et al. 2009). For each tagged juvenile, detections were ordered by date, time of day, and each Motus tower providing a full chronological profile of movement activity after the bird was no longer detected using manual radio telemetry at its natal site.

To determine fall migration dates for each of the tagged juveniles, we categorized the movements of each individual as either a premigration or fall migration movement. As the location of the study area is on the north shore of Lake Erie, we assumed that if a bird flew in a southerly direction across the lake (~50 km) that this must be a migratory movement. There were 27 tagged juveniles that were last detected by a tower within the study area and subsequently detected at a tower on the south side of Lake Erie on the same night and within a reasonable time frame (birds flying at ~50 km/h). We determined the average departure date and time of day of these individuals that were known to be undergoing their first migratory flight (avg. Sept. 19th, range Aug. 30^h to Sept. 29th). We used the R package *circular* (Agostinelli and Lund 2022) to analyze if the time of migratory flight departure was non-random, as would be expected for true migratory flights which typically occur just after sunset. As

expected, the time of day of these migratory movements was non-random ($\bar{R}= 0.654$, $p < 0.001$) and on average within 1 hr. and 18 mins. of local sunset.

Second, we used these times of first migratory flight results, to identify individuals who did not have detections the same night on both the north and south side of Lake Erie, but whose dates and time of day of departure were closely within the same range as the unambiguous fall migration movements. There were 55 individuals whose movements were categorized as a likely first migratory flight. These movements were also non-random ($\bar{R}= 0.609$, $p < 0.001$) with departures on average occurring at 21:05 about an hour after sunset (avg. departure date = Sept. 19, range = Aug. 25 to Oct. 15). We subsequently combined these 55 individuals with the unambiguous departures for analysis of departure date ($n = 82$). Using the Motus network, we determined fall migration departure date for 82 of 133 (62%) nestlings that were known to have survived the fledgling period.

Supplementary Material Table S8

Table S8. Motus tower locations outside of the study area for 6 juveniles that were detected the following spring after being radio-tagged. Tag ID 24 was detected in the study area on several occasions from May 24 to June 8 by 4 different Motus towers leading up to the final detection.

Motus Tag ID	Motus Tower	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Distance from Outer Perimeter of Study Area (km)	Date of Spring Motus Detection
211	Hagersville Landfill (Ontario)	42.9863	80.1281	28	May 31
24	Alymer (Ontario)	42.8005	80.946	28	June 8
373	West Port Bruce (Ontario)	42.6616	81.0627	30	May 9
18	Rondeau Provincial Park (Ontario)	42.2824	81.841	110	May 10
494	Presquelsle (Pennsylvania)	42.1098	80.1541	56	May 9
400	Girard (Pennsylvania)	41.9856	80.3379	65	May 22

Supplementary Material Table S9

Table 9. Summary of Wood Thrush apparent survival at three stages of the life cycle: (1) fledgling survival (up to 16 days after leaving the nest), (2) pre-migration survival (16 days after fledgling to fall migration period), and (3) migration/wintering survival (fall departure to spring arrival). First year annual survival was calculated from fledging to spring arrival the next year.

Tag Year	Total Tagged	Fledgling Survival (# fledglings survived (to 16d))	Pre-Migration Survival (# 16d old fledglings later detected on fall migration)	Migration/Wintering Survival (# juveniles detected on fall migration that returned the next spring)	Apparent Annual Survival
2016	47	33 (70.2%)	31 (93.9%)	10 (32.3%)	21.3%
2017	66	50 (75.8%)	42 (84.0%)	10 (23.8%)	15.2%
2018	76	50 (65.8%)	46 (92.0%)	11 (23.9%)	14.5%
<i>Total</i>	189	133 (70.4%)	119 (89.5%)	31 (26.1%)	16.4%